

IMPLICIT AND EXPLICIT FEATURES OF POLITENESS IN WRITTEN SPEECH IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK (ON THE EXAMPLE OF LETTERS)

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Abstract.

Introduction. *This article provides brief information about the features of expressing politeness in a written form that individual usually has a contact with one about something. Furthermore, it is given the explanation of the notion of the explicit and implicit features by the helping of proving with examples.*

Research methods. *Definitional analysis used in defining content some concepts that are significant for the work (for example, communicative category, politeness, communication etiquette, speech etiquette, communicative act, speech act, speech situation, communicative strategy, etc.). Contextual analysis, involving the study of ways expressions of politeness in the framework of a communicative situation, which forms a complex whole, including communicants with all their socio-demographic features and characteristics of their relationship among themselves, the environment in which the act of speech is performed, the theme of speech works, etc.*

Results and discussions. *During the article, several problems put in the discussion process and found recommendations and solutions. They are the age of individual which mostly people address with politeness (this is analysis by the helping of anonymous voting among the students of the university. Secondly, expressing politeness in an implicit or explicit way is actually converted with the linguocultural features of the language speakers.*

Conclusion. *At the end of the research, there has found the development and application of a new type of analysis to the study of the communicative category politeness along the line of explicitness and implicitness, presented, on the one hand, stereotypes of verbal*

communication, on the other hand, communication strategies of positive and negative politeness.

Key words. *Explicit, implicit, politeness, written form, letters.*

In the second half of the 20th century, linguistics changed vectors of scientific knowledge: to replace the structural level-by-level the description received systemic polyfunctional consideration linguistic/non-linguistic phenomena. The focus of scientists has been the functional side of the language, i.e. language in its speech embodiment. In this regard, the consideration of language/speech from the standpoint of anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics.

The communicative-pragmatic category of **politeness** as one of objects of language research in its speech incarnation in line with new linguistic directions helps to reveal the mechanism of human relationships and explain ways to achieve communicative goals in human speech communication. Politeness regulates communicative interaction of communicating, prescribing certain norms and traditions of verbal/non-verbal behavior (through communication etiquette) and regulating the relationship of people in various forms of communication - interpersonal, group, mass (through communication strategies). Thus, the implementation politeness in communication is closely related to the characteristics of communicative behavior and communicative consciousness of one or another linguocultural community. Numerous works representing various aspects consideration of the category of politeness served as a theoretical and methodological basis for this study.

In English linguistics, in particular, the theory of politeness¹³ has been studied by discovering the principles of power and solidarity. In this regard, R. Brown and A.

¹³Турдиева Х.К. Нуткий этикет бирликларининг лингвопрагматик тадқиқи (форс ва ўзбек тилларидаги материаллар асосида): Филол. фан. номз. ... дисс. – Тошкент, 2020. – Б. 13.

Gilman, R. Effective research by Brown and M.Ford, S.M.Ervin-Tripp, A.J.Vuton, K.Poynton, L.A.Wood, E.Dickey, M.Formotelli, J.Lich, M.Klein¹⁴ passes.

The actual linguistic aspect of the study of politeness is associated with the study of this category on the lexical, morphological, syntactic levels, as well as with a description of the functional and semantic characteristics of units representing the phenomenon courtesy (the works of E.I. Belyaeva, N.L. Sokolova, N.I. Formanovskoy, S. Feyrer, W. Gladrow, M. Haase, M. Hartig, G. Held, P. Klotz, N.-N. Luger, F. Ortu, O. Panagl, R. Rathmayr, J. Rehbein, K. Vorderwülbecke, H. Weydt, K. Zimmermann and others).¹⁵ If the linguistic aspect involves the study of verbal means of implementing politeness, then by studying its non-verbal expression engages in non-verbal semiotics, which analyzes kinesic, proxemic, paralinguistic, tactile, olfactory, etc. means of manifestation of politeness (see the works of L.I. Alekseeva, V.A. Labunskaya, G.V. Kolshansky, G.E. Kreidlin and others).

Based on explicit and implicit modes of expression courtesy, this communicative category is considered by us as a dual phenomenon associated:

- 1) with the observance of conventional norms and rules of communicative behavior (explicit, or conventional politeness);
- 2) with the implementation of positive and negative politeness (implicit or individual politeness).

In this regard, we define politeness as a central and fundamental category of communicative consciousness, content which is, on the one hand, a set of standardized norms and rules of social behavior regulating communicative interaction of those who communicate, on the other hand, a system of communicative strategies of positive and negative politeness aimed at harmonious, conflict-free communication. The units of analysis were, first of all, the formulas of speech etiquette, which are stable clichéd phrases and used in standard situations of communication. Speech units etiquette are

¹⁴ Lakoff R. The logic of politeness: or minding your p's and q's // Paper from the Ninth Regional Meeting of the Chicago Linguistic Society. – Chicago, 1973. – P.292-305; Brown P. & Levinson S. Universals in Language usage: Politeness phenomena. – London: 1978. – P.56-310.

¹⁵ Аркадьевич Р. Г., Коммуникативная категория вежливости в немецкой лингвокультуре. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени доктора филологических наук: Уфа-2011.

statements, the study of which, by right M.M. Bakhtin, “is <...> of fundamental importance for overcoming simplistic ideas about speech life, about called "speech flow", about communication. <...> Moreover, the study statements as a real unit of verbal communication will allow to better understand the nature of language units (as a system) - words and suggestions”.¹⁶ M.T.Kodirova said that It should be noted that speech etiquette, firstly, constitutes the principles of politeness, and secondly, is the basis for the social management of various situations of daily communication.¹⁷ And, according to S.M.Mo'minov: the term speech etiquette conditionally as "communication behavior" and emphasizes that it is an integral part of the character of the nation, they are closely interrelated. Consequently, speech etiquette coordinates the communication system, revealing the national culture in speech.¹⁸

Thus, a comprehensive study of etiquette, especially its verbal component, contributed to the study of the explicit, or conventional courtesy and the communicative category of politeness explicated through the verbal component of the communicative etiquette, i.e. speech etiquette, thus it is verbalized in communication. However, politeness can also be realized implicitly, i.e. by the helping of communication strategies aimed at "familiar face" both the addresser and the addressee. The main components of the communicative act are communicants, whom we define as participants in communication, alternately acting as the addresser (speaker, sender, communicator) initiating the utterance, and as the addressee (communicator, recipient), combining the role of the listener and responding to the utterance of the addresser. Due to this communication act should be seen as a two-way process, associated not only with the intention of the speaker, but also with the reaction of the addressee speech, which indicates the reciprocity of the actions of communicants, expressed in the generation of speech and its perception with a subsequent reaction. That is why the study of the

¹⁶ Аркадьевич Р. Г. Коммуникативная категория вежливости в немецкой лингвокультуре. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени доктора филологических наук: Уфа-2011.

¹⁷ Qodirova M.T. Turli tizimli tillarda murojaatning kommunikativ – pragmatik aspekti (ingliz va o'zbek tillari asosida). Filalogiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dissertatsiyasi aftoreferati. Termiz – 2021.

¹⁸ Мўминов С.М. Ўзбек мулоқот хулқининг ижтимоий-лисоний хусусиятлари. Филолог.фанлари доктори. ... дис.автореф. – Т., 2000. – Б.12.

communicative act and everything communication process must be conducted taking into account the intention speaker and interlocutor's reactions.

Communication etiquette should be considered as one of the traditional forms of existence of national culture. The element of culture is a multifaceted phenomenon, including such components as: 1) etiquette of behavior, regulating the socially prescribed form of etiquette behavior, 2) appearance etiquette, i.e. socially prescribed form of etiquette appearance, 3) the verbal component, namely speech etiquette and 4) non-verbal component. If the first component of communication etiquette is etiquette behavior - associated with generally accepted norms and rules of behavior a person in society, or with the so-called etiquette rules, reflecting a polite attitude towards others, then the second component - appearance etiquette - regulates the requirements accepted in society for the appearance of those who communicate in certain communicative situations.

M.T.Kodirova proved that addressing to unfamiliar and familiar people with politeness is much more higher then addressing impolitely in Uzbek verbal and oral communications. Here is the analysis of 3 Uzbek novels: mainly their addressing parts in her research:¹⁹

This line graph will be examples of explicit and implicit features of politeness in Uzbek languages. In both features, Uzbek people address politely. Another analysis which is done for analyzing exactly at what age people address much more polite way.

¹⁹ M.T. Qodirova Turli tizimli tillarda murojaatning kommunikativ – pragmatik aspekti (ingliz va o'zbek tillari asosida). Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dissertatsiyasi aftoreferati. Termiz – 2021.

This is taken as an anonymous vote among the 90 master students of Termez State University on 22.03.2022. Below, it is given the result:

This result shows that the explicit and implicit features of politeness in written communication according to the ages of people depicts the highest percentage of the pie chart placed the all ages, respectively 40%. It means that Uzbek people always have a contact with someone in a polite way.

The conducted research on the ways of functioning of the explicit and implicit politeness led to the conclusion that in English language has developed a rich arsenal of metacommunicative tools for manifestations of polite, respectful attitude towards the interlocutor. Wherein explicit politeness is expressed using various lexical and grammatical ways, for example, using:

- 1) some adjectives (for example, *fine, nice, wonderful, good* etc.) as part of the formulas of greeting, farewell, thanks to: *Good morning! Good afternoon! Good evening! Good night! Good bye! Thank you very much!*
- 2) adjectives *good, well* in superlatives in speech gratitude acts: *best thanks!, Thanks, very good!*
- 3) pronouns *you* in speech acts of gratitude: *thank you!*
- 4) modal verbs when expressing a polite request, offers, invitations, advice, apologies, etc.: *you should stop smoking! Can you pass me the salt? Could you tell me the time? May I come in?*

- 5) contact and distant calls in expressive and incentive speech acts: *hello, John! Can I speak to Mary, please?*

From the given examples and common situations that can be used politeness in explicit and implicit ways, researcher is able to comprehend that in English language also has politeness when they communicate to unfamiliar people. On the other hand, if the individuals are familiar to them, they prefer to have a contact much more closer and informal way.

Coming to conclusion, both languages face explicit and implicit ways of expressing politeness in any situations such as: oral or verbal communications. English people prefer to communicate much more closer when the addressee is familiar, while Uzbek people prefer to communicate politely in both types of people. Moreover, It should be noted that label units implement the category explicit politeness with varying degrees of intensity, i.e. politeness acts as a “graded phenomenon”. Usage formulas explicating different levels of politeness due to pursuing certain goals by communicants, for example, providing attention, showing interest, softening the imposition, suggesting further motivation for action, etc.

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